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PROCEDURES IN TRANSLATING ENGLISH AND ROMANIAN TOURIST ADVERTISEMENTS

Inga Stoianova

*Free International University of Moldova
52, Vlaicu Pârcalab Street, Chişinău, Republic of Moldova
agnissto@mail.ru*

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Abstract. Advertising acts as a bridge between the consumer and producer, the bridge being more difficult to cross in case of multicultural world. Procedures applied in the process of advertisements translation make the original text interesting, vivid and expressive. Working with the content of tourism advertisements, the translator in principle does not limit himself in the choice of translation transformations, however, modulation and descriptive translation are in the list of the most frequently used ones. Trying to translate any cultural or touristic reality as accurately as possible, the translator should always bear in mind that one of the most important tasks in translating this phenomenon is the preservation and transfer of the source text's color.

Key words: *advertisement, tourism, lexical and grammar transformations, methods and strategies of translation.*

Introduction

Language has powerful influence over people and their behavior. This is especially true in the fields of marketing and advertising. The study of advertising language and its grammar features is an important aspect in understanding how advertising is created, how it becomes effective and how it affects people and modern life. The choice of language to convey specific messages with the intention of influencing people is vitally important. Visual content and design in advertising have a very great impact on the consumer, but it is language that helps people to identify a product and remember it. The marketing and advertising personnel have to consider the emotive power of the words they use in advertising. There are several ways in which advertising is being used to persuade people to buy their product. Advertising unifies language, picture, music; it contains information, invokes emotions and imaginations, it can capture all five senses and, besides, it has social and practical aim [1].

Advertising is not easily defined, though many people have tried. Narrowly, it means a paid form of non-personal communication that is transmitted through mass media such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, direct mail, public transport vehicles, outdoor displays and also the Internet, which aims to persuade, inform, or sell. It flourishes mainly in free-market, profit-oriented countries. It is one of the most important factors in accelerating the distribution of products and helping to raise the standard of living. So three main objectives of advertising are: to product knowledge about the product or service, to create

preference for it, and to stimulate thought and action about it [2]. Advertisements are texts that do their best to get our attention, to make us turn towards them. Advertising unifies language, pictures, music; it contains information, invokes emotions and imaginations, it can capture all five senses and it has social and practical aim. The wide use of tourist advertising has created a special style of each language which unique characteristics, lexical units and important attraction makes it different from other kinds of languages.

English and Romanian tourist advertising exploits from the high adaptability of the languages. Both languages enable the creators of advertisements to use figurative language means, and to mix individual styles and types of texts. The wide use of various expressive means in the texts of tourist advertising helps the author of the original text to create a special one in the target language that is unforgettable to the reader, as well as to influence the recipient. These criteria should be taken into account by any translator who renders such types of texts as ignorance of certain features of advertising texts can lead to distortion of the translated text's message, and the consumer's interest in advertising decreases [2]. In our research a special attention is paid to the study of peculiarities of the English tourist advertising translation into Romanian preserving and ensuring equivalency.

It is known that the language of tourism conveys specific lexical, syntactic, functional and textual peculiarities and principles which differ from other specialized languages and which validate its categorization as a specialized discourse.

Translation of tourist advertisement texts should be carried out by professional skilled translators, as any other specialized translation, to avoid common mistakes encountered in these kinds of texts and to guarantee successful results. Some of the most common examples of these particular lexical, syntactic and textual features will be further discussed.

This article aims to explore the 'phraseology of tourism', i.e. lexical choices and recurring patterns in discourse [2]. English tourist internet discourse will be analyzed on the basis of the sites www.visitireland.com and www.autoeurope.com, while for the Romanian language www.travel.md will be supposed to investigation. English sites are world web sites available in different languages, including travel guides for various countries of Europe. Taken generally both Romanian and English sites include information of historical, natural, environmental order as well as modern and to - date aspects of the described places' life.

Methods of analysis

Before developing his/her own strategy of translation, any translator has to analyze carefully the texts on similar subject to understand the difficulties and aspects he/she might meet to take into account. Translation is known to be a complicated task, during which the meaning of the source-language text should be conveyed to the target-language readers. In other words, translation can be defined as encoding the meaning and form in the target language by means of the decoded meaning and form of the source language. Translation is an informational process as the translator should render information transmitted as fully as possible. This can be achieved only if certain structural and semantic changes are introduced. These changes, which are caused by lexical and grammatical differences between languages (and broadly speaking – by the differences between the respective cultures), are called transformations in translation [3].

Analysis and interpretation

Transference is the process of directly transferring a source language word to a target language text unchanged to create some particular stylistic effect. This strategy is preferred

when the translator wishes to keep the originality of the source text in his translation. Paul Newmark suggests that the usefulness of this strategy lies on its ability to “attract the reader, to give a sense of intimacy between the text and the reader - sometimes the sound or the evoked image appears attractive” [4]. Nevertheless, transference, though it is precise and brief, has been criticized for it “blocks comprehension, it emphasizes the culture and excludes the message, does not communicate; some would say it is not a translation procedure at all” [4]:

- ✓ *Areas of interest include Hampstead Heath and Primrose Hill with their huge green spaces, fabulous views and village feel./ Zonele de interes includ Hampstead Heath și Primrose Hill cu spații verzi imense, vederi fabuloase și aspectul rural.*
- ✓ *The South is appreciated for its array of open spaces such as Clapham Common, the World Heritage Site at Greenwich./Sudul este apreciat pentru o serie de spații deschise cum ar fi Clapham Common, site-ul Patrimoniului Mondial de la Greenwich.*

This type of transformation is mainly used in rendering geographical names or other types of precedent information.

Calque is actually a word or phrase borrowed from another language by literal, word-for-word translation. The term *calque* is borrowed from French and it derives from the verb *calquer* which means *to copy, to trace*. More specifically, we use the verb *to calque* when speaking about borrowing a word or phrase from another language while translating its components so as to create a new lexeme in the target language [5]. As calquing includes a degree of semantic translation, it does not consist of phonetic matching (i.e. retaining the approximate sound of the borrowed word by matching it with a similar-sounding pre-existing word or morpheme in the target language), for example: *mass tourism – turisimul de masă; city's green spaces – spațiile verzi a orașului; flea market – piață de vechituri; nightlife – viață de noapte; little Venice – Mica Veneție; seafood – produse de mare; day-trip – călătorie de o zi*. Here is an example of the sentence from the investigated site: *Dublin charms the visitor with a gorgeous coastal setting, compelling history, lively nightlife and an impressive food scene* [6]. /*Dublin atrage vizitatorul cu un peisaj costal superb, istorie convingătoare, viață de noapte vibrantă și o gamă impresionantă de feluri de bucate.*

Concretization is the process of changing words and collocations with broader meanings into words and collocations with narrower meanings. It is the choice of a more specific word in translation which gives a more detailed description of the idea than the word in the ST does. This kind of transformation can be called hyponymic as hypernym is changed into hyponym in the process of translation, e.g.: *Out East in Hampton, you're likely to find that the local cafe doubles as a hairdresser, a bookstore or a vintage clothes shop* [7]. /*La est de Hampton, probabil veți vedea că cafeneaua locală poate fi în același timp salon de coafură, librărie sau un magazin de haine de epocă.* In this case the translator used concretization to emphasize the idea that all the locals out of Hampton are not the districts of the Hampton city.

Generalisation is the phenomenon opposite to concretization, namely, the change of SL lexical units which have narrow meanings into the TL lexical units with broader meanings. This kind of transformation can be called hypernymic as hyponym is changed into hypernym in the process of translation, e.g.: *Oxford also has a thriving student population.* /*De asemenea, Oxford are o populație numeroasă de studenți.* In this case the translator does not specify the literal meaning of the word *thriving/înfloritor*, he generalizes it under the syntagm *populație numeroasă*. This type of transformation is not so frequently used in ads as it leads to the loss of figurativeness and colour of offers in the original.

Modulation basically means using a phrase that is different in the source and target languages to convey the same ideas. It obviously changes the semantics and shifts the point of view of the source language [5]. Modulation helps the translator generate a change in attitude of the message without altering its meaning and without generating an unnatural feeling in the reader of the target text: *And for those who just like strolling around and making the most of the good weather, there is also the option of relaxing on one of the café loungers set up along the river banks* [7]. / *Și pentru cei cărora le place să se plimbe și să profite la maximum de timpul frumos, există și opțiunea de a se relaxa într-unul din șezlongurile pe lângă cafenelelor, amplasate de-a lungul fluviului.* In the original text the author uses the expression *make the most of the good weather* literally translated as *a face la maximum vremea bună*. However, the translator refuses to follow this equivalent and suggests his own variant *să profite la maximum de timpul frumos*.

Another appealing sample deals with a polysemantic syntagm: *Discover the vibrant energy and multiple faces of this wonderful city.* / *Descoperiți energia vibrantă și diversitatea acestui oraș minunat.* It is interesting to note that the expression *multiple faces of the city* is better rendered into Romanian as *diversitatea acestui oraș* as the concept of multiple faces supposes cultural, ethical, economical diversity of the city.

In addition, in some cases, modulation helps to preserve the conversational expressions characteristic to the source text, e.g.: *Of course, in student communities this is more tolerated, but generally, you are most respected if you party as hard as you like- but with a sense of discretion and self-control* [7]. – *Desigur, în comunitățile studențești acest lucru este mai tolerat, dar, în general, deveniți cel mai popular dacă vă distrați la maximum - neuitînd de discreție și de auto-control.* Common verbal unit *party as hard as you like* has not a direct equivalent in Romanian, but it was translated as *a se distra la maximum*, which helped to preserve informal communicative value of the translated unit.

Omission means dropping a word or words from the source language text while translating. This procedure can be the outcome of the cultural clashes that exist between the SL and the TL [4]. The translator omits words that do not have equivalents in the TT, or that may raise the hostility of the receptor, for example: *When you first arrive in Manchester, try not to be put off by the city's ugly industrial outskirts* [7]. - *Când sosiți la Manchester pentru prima dată, încercați să nu vă speriați de suburbiile industriale ale orașului.* While performing the translation it was better to omit the word *ugly* in order to soften the message of the sentence and to preserve the touristic attractiveness of the city as “ugly” is something unpleasant or repulsive, especially in appearance which in no case should be associated to the tourist sights of any city. Another cause of omission might be the brevity of the advertisement discourse.

Word-for-word translation, also known as syntactic identity/literal translation, is the rendering of text from one language to another, one word at a time with or without conveying the sense of the original text. In translation studies, literal translation is often associated with specialized texts. A word for word translation can be used in some languages and not others dependent on the sentence structure. However, as one sentence can be translated literally across languages it does not mean that all sentences can be translated literally. Here are some examples from the field of tourism:

- ✓ *Walk along the River Lagan, and you'll enter the heart of Belfast's industrial past, when it was once one of the greatest places in the world for shipbuilding* [7]. / *Mergeți de-a lungul râului Lagan și veți nimeri în inima trecutului industrial al Belfast-ului, care fusese pe timpuri unul dintre cele mai mari centre de construcții navale din lume.*

- ✓ *You won't go far in the city without hearing a tune, whether it's from talented buskers on Grafton Street or traditional music coming from a pub. - Nu veți ieși departe în oraș fără a auzi o melodie fie că este vorba de flașnetarii talentați de pe strada Grafton, fie de muzica tradițională care se aude dintr-un pub.*

Partitioning is breaking an original sentence into two parts or replacing a simple sentence in the original with a complex one in translation, comprising one or several subordinate clauses. This is used in order to make the translated sentence more colourful, exciting, preserving the syntactical rules of the target language: *Best explored on foot, Cork is the kind of city that has a little bit of everything, including artsy enclaves and the historic Huguenot district* [4]. Here the Participial construction *best explored on foot* is translated into Romanian as an independent sentence following the syntactical order of the target language: *Cel mai bun mod de a descoperi orașul Cork este să o faci mergând pe jos. Cork este un oraș care are puțin din toate, incluzând enclave artistice și cartierul istoric Huguenot.*

Grammatical difficulties in the text mainly occur when there is dissimilarity between the SL and TL grammatical forms. Obviously, a permanent grammatical equivalence can be barely achieved, and the translator has to use one or several grammatical transformations.

Grammatical replacement is the translator's refusal to use analogous grammatical units in the target text. He tries to render the meaning of SL units by changing the grammatical form of a word, the part of speech or the type of the sentence. In rendering tourism texts the most common are the cases when the morphological categories of the members of the sentences are changed: *With a beautiful location on an island at the mouth of the River Lee, the city serves up a bustling blend of cafés and restaurants* [7]...- *Fiind amplasat pe o insulă frumoasă la gura râului Lee, orașul prezintă o combinație colorată de cafenele și restaurante.* Here the syntagmatic unit *with a beautiful location* under the formula Preposition + Article + Adjective + Noun was rendered into Romanian as a Participial verbal construction *fiind amplasat*, which is opposed to its mot-a-mot equivalent *cu o locație frumoasă*.

The following short sentence under the analysis includes a set of attractive tourist lexical structures: *Liverpool boasts a rich music history as the birthplace to the Beatles. - Orașul Liverpool se mândrește cu o istorie fascinantă a muzicii, fiind orașul de baștină a grupului Beatles.* In English the verb *to boast* (V) means "to be proud in the possession of something" [8], its Romanian equivalent being *a se mândri* (V), using the literal translation procedure for rendering the information into the target language. Compound English noun *birthplace* is translated into Romanian as a word combination *orașul de baștină* (N + prep + N), while *calque* is used as a translation procedure.

Mănăstirea Curchi /Curchi Monastery is one of the most important architectural monuments of Bessarabia, and it is also considered to be one of the most beautiful and famous monasteries of the region. It is a real small paradise place located not far from Chisinau, and every year many tourists come to visit this beautiful little town: *Mănăstirea Curchi este o mănăstire de călugări din Republica Moldova, una din cele mai însemnate monumente ale arhitecturii basarabene* [9]./ *The Curchi Monastery is a friary from the Republic of Moldova, one of the most important Moldovan architectural monuments.* This simple sentence is rendered using literal translation procedure, preserving cultural peculiarities of the national description of the monastery. However, the issue is the word combination *o mănăstire de călugări* (article + N + article + N) translated into English by a single word *a friary*, involving the transposition procedure of translation. To be mentioned that in English the lexical unit

friary has a collective meaning, in Romanian *o mănăstire de călugări* describes the place where many *friars* may live and spend their days.

Various syntactic transformations were also found. It is known that English has a strict, fixed word order: the subject is given first followed by the verb, the object and the adverbial(s). In English the adjective always precedes the nouns, comparing to Romanian where the adjective follows the substantival category of lexical units. Further the English qualifying adjective and Participles change their place in Romanian according to the rules of the target language grammar: *Today, crashing Atlantic waves, soaring hills and fascinating legends that tell of warring giants make visiting this UNESCO World Heritage Site an experience to cherish* [7].- *Astăzi, valurile nimicitoare ale oceanului Atlantic, dealurile înalte și legendele fascinante care relatează despre giganții războinici, transformă vizitarea acestei unități a patrimoniului mondial protejat de UNESCO într-o experiență de neuitat.* While translating English *crashing Atlantic waves* as *valurile nimicitoare ale oceanului Atlantic*, not only the order of the lexical units included in the syntagm has to be modified, but also the method of addition is involved, namely, introducing the word *ocean* in its Romanian equivalent (implicitly present in English variant) as well as the case of the phrase *UNESCO World Heritage Site* equivalent to *unități a patrimoniului mondial protejat de UNESCO*, Romanian *protejat* being absent in the original. In other cases there is the change of the qualifying adjectives and Participial constructions' place *soaring hills, fascinating legends, warring giants (dealurile înalte și legendele fascinante, războinici giganți)*. The lexical unit *experience to cherish* is rendered using antonymic translation *experiență de neapreciat*. According to the Oxford dictionary the verb *to cherish* is to keep (a hope or ambition) in one's mind [7], its equivalent in Romanian being *a îngriji, a prețui, a aprecia, a ține minte*. However, the Romanian variant *a ține minte* is too vague and indifferent to be applied in the translation of this sentence, while the lexical unit *de neuitat* (according to DEX "care nu se poate uita; a cărui amintire a rămas neștersă; vrednic de aducere-aminte, memorabil") has a more powerful emotional impact on the reader [8].

Pluralia and Singularia Tantum. In English-Romanian translation the cases of missing Plural or Singular noun forms are also worth paying attention to because of their frequent mismatch. These cases are, of course, shown in the dictionaries that is why several examples seem to be sufficient to illustrate this minor translation problem: *open skies – sub cer liber; serious partying – petreceri mari; Belgian chocolates – ciocolată belgiană* etc. Let's analyze one more syntactic instance: *This remote and unspoiled headland is Ireland's most northerly point (next stop – the Arctic Circle) and it's well known for its clear skies and lack of light pollution, making it a perfect place to spot the Northern Lights* [7]. - *Această regiune îndepărtată și neprihănită este punctul cel mai nordic al Irlandei (următoarea oprire - Cercul Arctic) și este bine cunoscută pentru cerul său limpede, lipsa oricărei poluări, făcându-l un loc perfect pentru a contempla Aurora Boreală.* Here besides the grammatical change of the noun *skies /cer*, there are some other appealing translational challenges to be discussed. Lexical unit *unspoiled headland* having the meaning of "not spoiled, in particular (of a place) not marred by development" translated as "nealterat, nestrucăt" cannot be applied to the natural environment. Meanwhile, Romanian *neprihănit*, i. e. "care este fără prihană, fără păcat, fără vină, pur, curat, nepătat, imaculat" best of all matches the stylistic value of the advertising message [10]. One more appealing lexical unit is *to spot* as to see something, but the verb is applied to the Northern Lights, a wonderful natural light display in the Earth's sky, predominantly seen in the high-latitude regions, and known for its unbelievable beauty. To our mind the best variant for *to spot the Northern Lights* would be *a contempla Aurora Boreală*.

According to DEX Romanian verb *a contempa is* “a (se) privi lung (cu admirație și cu emoție)”, perfectly matching the idea of the advertising [10].

Finally, there is a group of transformations which ensure the required degree of equivalence by a number of changes of both lexical and grammatical nature. They involve a different arrangement of ideas, a different point of view and other semantic modifications whenever a direct translation of a SL unit proves impossible. The group of lexico-grammatical transformations consists of antonymic and explanatory translation.

Antonymic translation usually implies a comprehensive lexical and grammatical transformation: an affirmative construction is translated by a negative one or a negative construction – by an affirmative one [4]. But such grammatical transformation is usually accompanied by the lexical one – the key word of the SL utterance is translated by its antonym in the TL utterance, for example:

- ✓ *Cultural life goes on all the year round in this place* [9]. - *Viața culturală nu încetinește pe nici o clipă.*
- ✓ *Don't miss the works of Vermeer, Frans Hals, and Rembrandt.* – *Neapărat să admirați/ vizionați lucrările de Vermeer, Frans Hals și Rembrandt.*

In the second sentence imperative mood *Don't miss the works* sounds as an order with a strong emotional effect, while its Romanian equivalent *neapărat să admirați/ vizionați* has a soft value of a piece of advice, a kind of recommendation which is given by the expert to the tourist.

Descriptive/explanatory translation consists of translating a source language/text word using a description of the concept it refers to in the target language; the successfulness of its integration into the prevailing linguistic norms of the target culture is always taken into account. In *It's an amazing and humbling place/ Este un loc uimitor unde te simți ca o furnică* the English syntagm *humbling place* cannot be translated into Romanian as *loc umilitor* as lexical unit *umilitor* has the meaning “care umilește, înjosește, ofensează; înjositor, jignitor”, the value of the word dealing with size. Its best Romanian equivalent is “a fi / a se simți ca o furnică”, namely very small, tiny.

Another challenging example of descriptive translation (plus addition technique) in the following sentence refers to the quality of the Irish restaurant: *Set in the heart of the Comber countryside (famous for its potato, the Comber Early), this luxury guest house and restaurant has earned a Michelin Bib Gourmand for creative, quality cooking* [6].- *Amplasat în inima ținutului Comber (Comber Early este faimos pentru cartofii săi), această pensiune și restaurantul de lux a câștigat un Michelin Bib Gourmand (top cel mai bun restaurant mic cu prețuri accesibile și mâncare de bună) pentru bucătărie creativă și de calitate.* In this sentence the lexical unit *un Michelin Bib Gourmand* represents a Michelin's version of "cheap eats," the bib gourmand awards feature restaurants at which you can get two courses plus a dessert or a glass of wine for under \$40 (tax and tip not included). The tourist might not know the semantic value and the gastronomical world importance of the ranking, so the translator gives a description in brackets.

Conclusions

In the process of translation, it is necessary to remember about its specifics, namely, that the advertisement is addressed to the mass consumer and must have the character of persuasion. A high degree of communication focus on the object of advertisement is expressed not only in the way the information is transmitted, but also in influencing human

feelings and emotions in order to evoke a positive reaction. Creating a personal interest in the reader is achieved by using various language means of expressiveness. Therefore, translation of tourist advertising texts is complicated by the combination of cognitive and expressive information; the translator needs to grasp the line between these two aspects. The advertising component of tourist ads is no less important and complex for translation than information. It is significant to maintain the degree of advertising that the source texts has. The communicative task is often complicated by the fact that the translator needs to ensure that it is carried out to the same extent as in the original.

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